

RARE PIGMENTARY ANOMALY OF MOUNTAIN CORAL SNAKE *Micrurus mipartitus rozei* (SERPENTES: ELAPIDAE) IN YARACUY STATE, VENEZUELA

RARA ANOMALÍA PIGMENTARIA DE LA SERPIENTE CORAL DE MONTAÑA *Micrurus mipartitus rozei* (SERPENTES: ELAPIDAE) EN EL ESTADO YARACUY, VENEZUELA

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ABSTRACT

Documented information about chromatic anomalies in snakes of the genus *Micrurus* is scarce, although these variations in pigmentation patterns are of great interest to understand how changes in developmental mechanisms can give rise to diverse patterns. In this article, we report the occurrence of a piebaldism-type pigmentary anomaly in *Micrurus mipartitus rozei* (Serpentes: Elapidae), characterized by the reduction of melanophores locally, in that the black rings arranged along the body are incomplete ventrally.

KEY WORDS: Chromatophores, piebaldism, color pattern, venomous snakes, Cerro María Lionza Natural Monument.

RESUMEN

Información documentada acerca de anomalías cromáticas en serpientes del género *Micrurus* son escasas, a pesar de que estas variaciones en los patrones de pigmentación son de gran interés para entender cómo los cambios en los mecanismos de desarrollo pueden dar diversos patrones. En este artículo, se reporta la ocurrencia de una anomalía pigmentaria de tipo piebaldismo en *Micrurus mipartitus rozei* (Serpentes: Elapidae), caracterizada por la reducción de melanóforos localmente, en la que los anillos negros dispuestos a lo largo del cuerpo son incompletos ventralmente.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Cromatóforos, piebaldismo, patrón de coloración, serpiente venenosa, Monumento Natural Cerro María Lionza.

Snakes exhibit diverse, complex, and polymorphic coloration patterns that have evolved in response to ecological and physiological conditions (Allen *et al.* 2013). Nowadays, chromatic aberrations or anomalies in snakes are increasingly documented worldwide, particularly in South America (Borteiro *et al.* 2021). However, cases recorded in Venezuela remain relatively rare (Esqueda *et al.* 2005, Vargas 2015, Esqueda *et al.* 2025), although they have also been observed in other reptiles (Romero-Briceño 2018). These chromatic variations are primarily attributed to genetic alterations that affect the phenotype of individuals, leading to atypical coloration linked to changes in their chromatophores (Bechtel 1978). Beyond the simple presence or absence of pigments, much of the color and pattern variation in snakes is complex and is best represented as a quantitative trait (Cox *et al.* 2023). In the genus *Micrurus*, chromatic anomalies have been documented less frequently. Some examples include: dorsal spots on the body instead of rings in *M. fulvius fulvius*

(Meachen & Myers 1961); melanistic patterns in *M. fulvius tenere* (Gloyd 1938); hyperxanthism in *M. fulvius fulvius* (Smith *et al.* 1970); amelanism in *M. lemniscatus* and *M. pyrrhocryptus*; erythrism and anerythrism in *M. corallinus* (Borteiro *et al.* 2021); and piebaldism in *M. tener*, which presents unusual dorsal blotches or a target pattern (Farr & Warren 2013).

Micrurus mipartitus rozei Golay, Chiszar, Smith & Breukelen, 1999 is a coral snake distributed across the central stretch of the Cordillera de la Costa and the Lara-Falcón Mountain System in Venezuela (Natera-Mumaw *et al.* 2015). On July 20, 2005, at 10 AM, an active adult female specimen was observed 150 meters from a stream at Cerro El Sorte, within the Cerro María Lionza Natural Monument, Yaracuy state (10°10'12" N, 68°89'85" W; 700 m asl, evergreen forest) (Fig. 1). It was collected and deposited in the Estación Biológica Rancho Grande Museum (EBRG 7126). This specimen exhibited atypical coloration: a

completely white ventral region lacking black rings (Fig. 2A) and a dorsum with the typical bicolor pattern of the species (Savage & Slowinski 1992). Following the complete red nuchal ring, the remaining 52 black rings (4–5 scales wide) barely reached the ventral region, although they varied toward the cloaca and had rounded edges; black rings from the cloaca to the tail were complete. Additionally, a *Bachia heteropa* (elongated-bodied lizard) was found in the digestive tract. At the same location, another female specimen with a bicolor pattern (EBRG 7125) was also collected. It had 51 complete black rings, 4–5 scales wide, interspersed with white rings one scale wide toward the vertebral region, which progressively widened ventrally. The area corresponding to the red nuchal ring was white, and two black rings near the tail were incomplete (Fig. 2B-C).

Although the structural combination and interaction of pigment cells determine skin color in Squamates (Kuriyama *et al.* 2020), melanophores (responsible for black-brown coloration) appear first during embryogenesis, defining the initial framework of striped patterns in some species (Kuriyama *et al.* 2006, Murakami *et al.* 2017). In more complex patterns, like those of coral snakes, a cellular chemotaxis model is one of the best mechanisms to explain melanophore migration and differentiation in pattern formation (Murray & Myerscough 1991, Murakami *et al.* 2017). Under this scenario, anomalous color patterns in reptiles such as snakes are generally associated with hypopigmentation (reduced or absent pigments, e.g.,

black eumelanin) or hyperpigmentation (excess pigmentation) (Borteiro *et al.* 2021). In the case reported here, the anomaly is best explained by the reduction or absence of black eumelanin, an instance of piebaldism, where black rings are missing along the ventral side of the body.

Although chromatic aberrations have been reported in other *Micrurus* species, this is the first documented case of piebaldism in a coral snake from Venezuela, with a bicolor pattern and entirely white ventral surface, rather than black rings alternating with white ones. However, previous taxonomic reviews have noted some related patterns, such as incomplete body triads in *M. spixii* (Nascimento *et al.* 2019) and incomplete bicolor patterns in *M. diastema* (Fraser 1973). For instance, Stafford (2000) reported incomplete black rings in 6.5% of *M. nigrocinctus*, 31.3% of *M. diastema*, and 48.5% of *M. hippocrepis*, although without specifying whether the incompleteness occurred dorsally or ventrally. Chromatic anomalies may be more common in coral snakes or their mimics than current literature suggests. The adult condition of the specimen reported here implies that hypopigmentation is not strongly disadvantageous in reptiles with cryptozoic and/or fossorial habits (Borteiro *et al.* 2021, Allain *et al.* 2023, Paiva *et al.* 2023). In fact, a photograph of an adult *Micrurus isozonus* from Venezuela (locality unknown, Luis Merlo, pers. comm.) shows an anomalous dorsal pattern where white or black rings partially or completely disappear, leaving a red ring with sparse black pigmentation over the scales (Fig. 2D).

Figure 1. Geographical location of the sighting in the state of Yaracuy, Venezuela.

Figure 2. *Micrurus mipartitus rozei*: specimen EBRG 7126, adult female with the aberrant pattern of incomplete black rings on the body (A-B: Canon EOS Rebel T6, objetivo 55 m) and specimen EBRG 7125, adult female with the typical bicolor pattern, consisting of alternating black and white rings on the body (C: Canon EOS Rebel T6, objetivo 55 m). Finally, a specimen of *Micrurus isozonus* photographed in life, © Luis Merlo (D: Canon 7D, macro lens 100 mm).

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REFERENCES

ALLAIN SJR, CLEMENS DJ, THOMAS O. 2023. Taste the rainbow: a review of color abnormalities affecting the herpetofauna of the British Isles. *Reptiles & Amphibians*. 30:e18470.

ALLEN WL, BADDELEY R, SCOTT-SAMUEL NE, CUTHIL LI. 2013. The evolution and function of pattern diversity in snakes. *Behav. Ecol.* 24(5):1237-1250.

BECHTEL HB. 1978. Color and pattern in snakes. *J. Herpetol.* 12(4):521-532.

BORTEIRO C, ABEGG AD, ODA FH, CARDOZO D, KOLENC F, ETCHANDY I, BISAIZ I, PRIUGINI C, BALDO D. 2021. Aberrant colourations in wild snakes: case study in neotropical taxa and a review of terminology. *Salamandra*. 57(2):124-138.

COX CL, RABOSKY DAR. 2023. The integrative biology of snake coloration. Chapter 5. *In: PENNING D. (Ed). Snakes: Morphology, function,*

- and ecology. Nova Science Publishers, Hauppauge NY, USA, pp. 179-217.
- ESQUEDA LF, LA MARCA E, SORIANO P. 2005. Partial albinism in a Venezuelan specimen of false coral snake *Oxyrhopus petola petola* (Linnaeus, 1758). *Herpetotropicos*. 2(2):65.
- ESQUEDA LF, BAZÓ S, ORTIZ JC. 2025. Albinism in the snail-eating snake *Sibon nebulatus* (Dipsadidae: Dipsadini) within an urban area in the Venezuelan Andes. *Saber*. 35:96-99.
- FARR WM, WARREN T. 2013. Natural history: *Micrurus tener* (Texas coralsnake). *Herpetolog. Rev.* 44(4):694-695.
- FRASER DF. 1973. Variation in the coral snake *Micrurus diastema*. *Copeia*. 1(1):1-17.
- GLOYD HK. 1938. A case of poisoning from the bite of a black coral snake. *Herpetologica*. 1(5):121-124.
- KURIYAMA T, MIYAJI K, SUGIMOTO M, HASEGAWA M. 2006. Ultrastructure of the dermal chromatophores in a lizard (Scincidae: *Plestiodon latiscutatus*) with conspicuous body and tail coloration. *Zool. Sci.* 23(9):793-799.
- KURIYAMA T, MURAKAMI A, BRANDLEY M, HASEGAWA M. 2020. Blue, black, and stripes: evolution and development of color production and pattern formation in lizards and snakes. *Front. Ecol. Evol.* 8(232):1-4.
- MEACHEM A, MYERS CW. 1961. An exceptional pattern variant of the coral snake, *Micrurus fulvius* (Linnaeus). *Q. J. Florida Acad. Sci.* 24(1):56-58.
- MURAKAMI A, HASEGAWA M, KURIYAMA T. 2017. Developmental mechanisms of longitudinal stripes in the Japanese four-lined snake. *J. Morphol.* 279(1):27-36.
- MURRAY JD, MYERSCOUGH MR. 1991. Pigmentation pattern formation on snakes. *J. Theor. Biol.* 149(3):339-360.
- NASCIMENTO LRS, SILVA JR NJ, FEITOSA DT, PRUDENTE ALC. 2019. Taxonomy of the *Micrurus spixii* species complex (Serpentes, Elapidae). *Zootaxa*. 4668(3):370-392.
- NATERA-MUMAW M, ESQUEDA GONZÁLEZ LF, CASTELAÍN FERNÁNDEZ M. 2015. Atlas Serpientes de Venezuela. Una Visión Actual de su Diversidad. Primera edición. Imprenta Dimacofi Negocios Avanzados, Santiago de Chile, Chile, pp. 456.
- PAIVA C, VAN DER WINDEN J, BOGAERTS S, COSTA H. 2023. A review of chromatic anomalies in *Blanus* (Amphisbaenia: Blanidae) through citizen science records. *Turk. J. Zool.* 47(5):315-318.
- ROMERO-BRICEÑO JC. 2018. Un caso de xantismo en *Chelonoidis carbonaria* (Spix, 1824) (Testudines: Testudinidae) en los Llanos centrales de Venezuela. *Mem. Fund. La Salle de Cs. Nat.* 76(84):103-107.
- VARGAS C. 2015. Leucismo en la serpiente rabo amarillo (*Drymarchon corais*) (Boie, 1827), (Serpentes: Colubridae), estado Lara, Venezuela. *Bol. Centro Invest. Biol.* 49(2):174-178.
- SAVAGE JM, SLOWINSKI JB. 1992. The colouration of the venomous coral snakes (family Elapidae) and their mimics (families Aniliidae and Colubridae). *Biol. J. Linnean Soc.* 45(3):235-254.
- SMITH H, ALLEN ER, HOLLAND RL. 1970. A new atavistic hyperxanthic chromotype in the coralsnake *Micrurus fulvius* (Linnaeus). *J. Herpetol.* 4(1/2): 80-83.
- STAFFORD PJ. 2000. On the status of the coral snake *Micrurus nigrocinctus* (Serpentes: Elapidae) in Belize, and its northernmost distribution in Atlantic Middle America. *Herpetol. Rev* 31(2):78-82.